

INSTALLATION OF OSSEOINTEGRATED IMPLANTS FOR PROSTHETICS OF PARTIAL AND COMPLETE LOSS OF TEETH USING A SURGICAL TEMPLATE

Aliyev V.I.

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine,
Azerbaijan Medical University, hourly paid teacher
Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, Assistant
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

The article presents data on the features of planning the installation of implants and the technology of using a surgical template for positioning the installation of dental implants. Target. Show the importance of using surgical templates for the rational installation of dental implants and the prevention of possible errors and complications. Main advantages: accurate placement of implants, preservation of anatomical structures, three-dimensional technology allows to accurately assess anatomical points, such as the size of the maxillary sinus in the upper jaw and the location of the alveolar nerve in the lower jaw, high observed accuracy of 0.1 mm, reduced surgical intervention time. Disadvantages: lack of visibility and tactile control during the surgical procedure, insufficient degree of mouth opening jeopardizes the result of complex treatment, there is a risk of damage to vital anatomical structures.

Keywords: implantation, surgical template, cylindrical implant, computer planning.

Prosthetics for partial and complete loss of teeth using osseointegrated implants is becoming more and more popular and in demand today, more and more dentists use computer-aided planning of implant placement using a surgical template [1]. This involves radiographic assessment of the height and width of the available bone for implant placement or during surgical procedures to provide space for optimal placement of the implant. The use of surgical templates when placing implants undoubtedly helps the surgeon to use biomechanically justified places from the point of view of the best occlusal load, aesthetics and hygiene requirements [2].

Improper implant placement is a very common dilemma that often complicates clinical laboratory steps. This actually requires close collaboration between prosthodontists and surgeons to work together as a team that will contribute to the accurate preparation of the surgical stage. However, planning an implant prosthesis is a challenge for function and esthetics. High accuracy in planning and performing surgical procedures is important to ensure a high degree of success without causing iatrogenic injury [3].

Computed tomography (CT), 3D implant planning software, graphic-guided template making, and computer-assisted surgery have made significant progress in treatment.

The template should be lightweight and freely overlap the surgical field, and should not obscure the surrounding surgical landmarks. [4] The surgical template should not contaminate the surgical field during bone grafting or implant placement. It should be transparent so that the bone ridge and surgical drills can be easily seen when the template is applied to the work area, and should also be in line with the ideal contour of the face. With significant atrophy of the alveolar processes and complete loss of teeth, the template can help determine the lost volumes necessary for implant placement or support for the lips and face. It can be used in combination with a bone graft and for the insertion and

opening of implants. The strength of the template allows it to be re-sterilized and used for several procedures [5]. Purpose — to show the importance of using surgical templates for the rational installation of dental implants and the prevention of possible errors and complications. The success of dental implants in patient care is directly related to patient assessment and accurate treatment planning. The surgical protocol for successful implant placement demonstrates osseointegration, the optimal position of the implant for the manufacture of a dental prosthesis from an aesthetic and functional point of view, and also requires obtaining diagnostic information about the state of bone structures and soft tissues in order to plan the optimal placement of the implant in three dimensions: buccal-lingual, mesio-distal, apical - crown. Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) is a relatively recently developed imaging technology for jawbone structures that uses lower radiation dose levels than conventional CT scanners. It differs from conventional computed tomography setups in such aspects as weight, cost, scan time, and final image resolution [6]. The negative aspects of CBCT are the relatively high cost of the procedure and the lack of accuracy in assessing soft tissues [11]. However, it is a method of examination for preoperative purposes, especially when the benefits to the patient offset the risks of exposure to ionizing radiation [7]. In addition to CBCT scanning, computer software is available to display and convert DICOM files (raw data generated by CBCT) into a high-quality 3D image, allowing clinicians to conduct diagnosis and treatment planning at a high level of accuracy. In addition, CT scanning software can improve communication within an interdisciplinary team between clinician and patient.

Current software applications have tools that allow clinicians to simulate implant placement using transection, panoramic, and 3D views. They allow diagnosing the morphology and quality of bones and identifying anatomical landmarks [8].

Purpose — to show the importance of using surgical templates for the rational installation of dental implants and the prevention of possible errors and complications. The success of dental implants in patient care is directly related to patient assessment and accurate treatment planning. The surgical protocol for successful implant placement demonstrates osseointegration, an aesthetically and functionally optimal implant position for denture fabrication, and requires access to display and convert DICOM (CBCT-generated raw data) files into a high-quality 3D image, allowing clinicians to diagnose and treatment planning at a high level of accuracy.

The main purpose of the surgical template is to guide the implant drilling system and ensure accurate implant placement in accordance with the surgical treatment plan.

In the manufacture of radiographic surgical template, self-polymerization of acrylic resin is used. Espinosa Marino et al. showed the first clinical application of thermopolymerizing acrylic resin in the manufacture of a surgical guide, especially for partial loss of teeth. To make it radiopaque on CT scans, they applied a dual-curing composition mixed with colored chalk. Stellino et al. demonstrated pre-fixed restorations of acrylic resin using gutta-percha as an opaque marker [9]. Pezun and Gardner used a vacuum thermoplastic matrix to match the diagnostic model [10]. Surgical templates are made mainly on models of the jaws, which are a rigid non-functional surface without knowledge of soft tissue compliance and bone relief. In addition, anatomical landmarks are not exactly located. Even panoramic radiography has its own diagnostic limitations (dilation and distortion, placement error, positional artifacts) and there is no information regarding buccolingual bone size. CT images are converted into data that is recognized by imaging and implant planning software. According to the original Branemark protocol, the time period for implant osseointegration before restoration in preparation for loading was 3 to 6 months depending on implant position and bone quality. Stereolithography, a rapid prototyping technology, allows surgical guides to be made from 3D computer models for precise implant placement. Surgical templates made using this technology are pre-programmed with individual depth, angles, mesiodistant and labiolingual placement of the implant.

Benefits: accurate placement of implants; • preservation of anatomical structures; • 3D technology allows precise assessment of anatomical points such as the size of the maxillary sinus in the maxilla and the location of the alveolar nerve in the mandible; • Accurate analysis of bone topography provides information about the size, direction and location of the bone for accurate positioning of implants; • high accuracy (0.1mm); • reduction of time of surgical operation; • less invasive surgery and therefore less chance of complications; • transparency of the material, which allows you to see through the model; • The CT scan procedure is performed using a radiographic template made using a radio-opaque marker.

Disadvantages: • lack of visibility and tactile control during the surgical procedure; • Insufficient dis-

tance with the superimposed template for the physiodispenser and the surgical drill jeopardizes the success of the surgical stage; • risk of damage to vital anatomical structures.

Conclusion and recommendations

Improvements in surgical restorative techniques, as well as increased demands on prostheses, require highly accurate diagnosis, planning, and placement. The identification of bone anatomy in relation to teeth prior to surgery allows the clinician to place implants in areas where the implant bone interface can be maximized and prosthetic outcome optimized. For accurate planning of the positioning of implants and their precise placement during the surgical phase, the manufacture of a surgical template with guide sleeves is an obligatory step. This technology makes it possible to avoid most of the typical mistakes and complications, and most importantly, to improve the quality of treatment of partial and complete loss of teeth using implants.

References

1. Ryakhovskii, A.N. Varianty primeneniya napravlyayushchikh shablonov na khirurgicheskom etape dental'noi implantatsii / A.N. Ryakhovskii, S.V. Mikhas'kov // Panorama ortopedicheskoi stomatologii. – 2007. – №1. – S. 6–11.
2. Ispol'zovanie 3D planirovaniya i khirurgicheskogo shablona dlya profilaktiki nepravil'noi ustanovki tsilindricheskikh implantatov v kostnoi tkani chelyusti / S.E. Zholudev, P.M. Nersesyan, D.S. Zholudev, A.Yu. Remov // Problemy stomatologii. – 2016. – №2. – S. 79–85
3. Kola M.Z., Shah A.H., Khalil H.S., Rabah A.M. N. et al. Surgical Templates for Dental Implant Positioning; Current Knowledge and Clinical Perspectives. Niger J. Surg, 2015, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 1–5.
4. Ispol'zovanie 3D planirovaniya i khirurgicheskogo shablona dlya profilaktiki nepravil'noi ustanovki tsilindricheskikh implantatov v kostnoi tkani chelyusti / S.E. Zholudev, P.M. Nersesyan, D.S. Zholudev, A.Yu. Remov // Problemy stomatologii. – 2016. – №2. – S. 79–85.
5. Misch C.E. St. Louis, 3rd ed, Mosby Publications, 2007, Contemporary Implant Dentistry.
6. Giri R.M., Subramonian R.R., Narendrakumar K.R. Implant surgical guides: From the past to the present. J Pharm Bioallied Sci, 2013, vol. 5, pp. 98–102.
7. D'Souza K.M., Aras M.A. Types of implant surgical guides in dentistry: A review. J. Oral. Implantol, 2012, vol. 38, pp. 643–652.
8. Horwitz J., Zuabi O., Machtei E.E. Accuracy of a computerized tomography-guided template-assisted implant placement system: An in vitro study. Clin Oral Implants Res, 2009, vol. 20, pp. 1156–1162.
9. Borisov R. Radiological templates and CAD/CAM surgical guides. A literature review. Journal of IMAB - Annual Proceeding (Scientific Papers), 2016, vol. 22, iss. 3, pp. 1285–1295.
10. Block M.S., Emery R.W. Static or Dynamic Navigation for Implant Placement- Choosing the Method of Guidance. J. Oral. Maxillofac. Surg, 2016, vol. 74 (2), pp. 269–277.